

A Study of the thickness and ageing dependent variation in the electrochromic property of V₂O₅ xerogel thin films

Sajitha Surendren^{a, b}, Biswapriya Deb^{a, b*}

^aPhotosciences & Photonics Section, Chemical Science and Technology Division
CSIR-NIIST, Trivandrum 695019, India

^bAcademy of Science and Innovative Research (AcSIR), CSIR-NIIST, Thiruvananthapuram-695019, India

*Email: biswapriya.deb@niist.res.in

Abstract

Electrochromism is the reversible change in chromic response of materials with electrically concerted charge insertion/extraction. Because of their tenability, the electrochromic materials have widespread applications in the smart windows¹, solar energy modulators², display devices³ and variable emittance surface⁴ etc. Among these, V₂O₅ is extensively studied because of their several oxidation states that are adjacent to each other in the energy axes with distinctively different colors. In this work V₂O₅ xerogel thin films of various thicknesses were prepared by sol-electrophoresis. With an increase in the film thickness we observed a noticeable decrease in the optical band gap of the material (2.6 eV - 2.3 eV). The structural and morphological aspects were characterized using XRD, FTIR, SEM and TEM etc. Electrochromic devices (ECD) were fabricated using V₂O₅ xerogel thin films as electroactive layer and electro-optical responses were studied using UV-Visible spectroscopy, cyclic voltammetry and chronoamperometry. This study correlates how the ECD performance parameters such as coloration efficiency, color contrast and switching speed is greatly influenced by factors like thickness and ageing.

Keywords - V₂O₅ Xerogel, Electrophoretic deposition, Electrochromic device

References

1. Patil, R. et al, Sol. Energ. Mat. Sol. C. 147(2016), 240-245
2. Araki, S et al, Adv. Mater. 24(2012), 122-126
3. Mishra, S et al, J. Mater. Chem. C, 5(2017), 9504-9512
4. Demiryont, H et al, Sol. Energ. Mat. Sol. C. 93(2009), 2075-2078